

UNDERSTANDING MAJOR ISSUES OF SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract:

SLA is an interesting discipline of research. It deals with many integral process of learning a language. This paper is an attempt to explore the prominent factors involved in the SLA. A remarkable fact about the acquisition of language is the speed with which a child is able to acquire a language. Language is a complex phenomenon and a normal child masters this complexity with an astonishing speed and in circumstances usually less than ideal. The speed of language acquisition is not determined by the complexity of the language but the social environments in which a child starts acquiring the language. It also seeks to understand universal, individual and social forces that influence it. SLA also investigates into how fast, how well second language is acquired or learned by different people under different circumstances.

Key words: *Mother Tongue (MT), Target Language (TL), Interlanguage, Acquisition, Learning, Language Transfer, Process of Learning*

Introduction

Just as the definitions of monolingualism versus bilingualism are problematic, so are the definitions of the first language and the second language. In countries such as England and France, many children are socialized in a variety of the standard languages, and it seems clear what their first language is. But 'about half of the world's population is bilingual' (Grosjean, quoted in Romaine, 1989: 8), and for many people living in a country like India, it is not really clear what constitutes their first, second or third language. Children may learn one or two other languages at school, and later in life they may even learn and use again another language to such an extent that the first foreign language is no longer used and fades away. How 'second' and 'third' should be distinguished in such cases is unclear. Some linguists order languages in terms of level of proficiency, others in the order of the time of acquisition, but neither of these distinctions applies to children who have two or more languages from birth. In such cases first, second or third can be defined only in terms of settings of use (de Bot et al., 2005: 6).

The general definition of second language given by Ellis is quite appropriate and generic. He writes, '... the term "second" is generally used to refer to any language other than the first language' (Ellis, 1994: 11).

Second Language Acquisition (SLA)

SLA is the study of how second languages are learned. It is the study of how learner creates a new language system, about the degree of proficiency in second language and many more things. As a whole we can say SLA is the scholarly field of inquiry that investigates the human capacity to learn a language other than the first, during late childhood, adolescent or adulthood, and once the first language have been acquired. It seeks to understand universal, individual and social forces that influence it. SLA also investigates into how fast, how well second language is acquired / learned by different people under different circumstances.

Acquisition versus Learning

The impact of Krashen's input hypothesis in the field of second language acquisition and teaching has been profound. His hypothesis has been, to a large extent, responsible for the introduction of two of the most controversial issues in SLA theory and practice. These two issues are connected with the roles of input and grammar instruction in second language acquisition. Krashen's input hypothesis is an attempt to account for second language acquisition processes. It consists of five hypotheses: Acquisition-Learning, Natural Order, Monitor, Input, and Affective Filter (Krashen, 1985 cited in Johnson, 2004: 46-7).

Distinction between acquisition and learning has always been tricky and controversial in SLA literature. But the common definition which is found in most books is that acquisition is a product of subconscious process and learning is the product of conscious process. Krashen writes:

... acquisition [is] a process similar, if not identical to the way children develop ability in their first language. Language acquisition is a subconscious process; language acquirers are not usually aware of the fact that they are acquiring language but are only aware of the fact that they are using the language for communication.

(Krashen, 1982 quoted in Gass and Selinker, 2001: 198)

We will use the term "learning" henceforth to refer to conscious knowledge of a second language, knowing the rules, being aware of them, and being able to talk about them.

(Krashen, 1982 quoted in *ibid*).

Schmidt (1990) has given some counter arguments against Krashen's (1982) definitions of acquisition and learning. He argues that the term 'subconscious' may be misleading and it is not used in a technical sense because it refers to totally unaware process. But in spite of his counter argument Krashen's (1982) definitions are quite appropriate and widely acceptable. His definition stipulates that acquisition is a natural process of growth of knowledge and skill in a language. On the other hand learning is an artificial process in which the rules of the language are more on focus (de Bot et al., 2005: 9-10).

There are many scholars who use the terms "acquisition and learning" sinuously in their works, especially in contemporary SLA literature. In 1980s there was an attempt to distinguish the terms but there was no such distinction found. But the term acquisition is more widely used, the discipline itself called language acquisition because it has broader sense (Ortega, 2009: 5).

Some Factors Involved in SLA

Age: it is generally believed that children are better language learners than adults and children can get mastery over second language whereas adults cannot. It is one of the factors which are associated with the 'critical period hypothesis' (Lanneberg, cited in de Bot et al., 2005: 65). The hypothesis claims that it is difficult to acquire native-like competence in second language after puberty (critical age). It also claims that the late starter in second language may acquire native like competence in syntax and the vocabulary of it but it is impossible for them to achieve native-like pronunciation. So, we can say that children have better phonology (if they acquire second language) and adult learners have better syntax. But the age factor in SLA is still an open-ended question and the debate is going on among the scholars (Ortega, 2009: 12-30, Gass and Selinker, 2001: 335-344 and de Bot, 2005: 65-69).

Attitudes and Motivation: It is claimed by the scholars of SLA that high motivation and positive attitudes toward second language help in second language learning. The communities in which the second language learning takes place also help the learners. Orientation and attitudes vary according to the context in which it is learnt. For example, attitudes and motivation towards French and English is varied in India because English is taught in India as the second language and French as a foreign language.

Aptitude and Intelligence: Irrespective of age and motivation factors, some learners show themselves better at learning a second language. The inherent and innate capability of second language learning labeled as language learning aptitude. Aptitude is something that is similar to intelligence which cannot be changed (enhanced) through training. It is psychological formulation in human brain which helps in learning additional language (de Bot, 2005: 69-71 and Ortega, 2009: 145: 167). Aptitude, according to de Bot, is usually described as a combination of four factors:

1. the ability to identify and remember sounds of the foreign language;
2. the ability to recognise how words function grammatically in sentences;
3. the ability to induce grammatical rules from language examples;
4. and the ability to recognise and remember words and phrases.

(de Bot, 2005: 69)

Interlanguage

‘Interlanguage’ is the language produced by a non-native speaker of a language (Selinker, 1974: 31). It is a language system created by the second language learners. A second language learner uses different interlanguages at different stages of his learning as he seldom achieves native-like competence in target language. After achieving a certain stage of learning, the learner stops learning irrespective of the training and exposure of the target language and this phenomenon is known as ‘fossilization’. According to Selinker, ‘... the existence of a separate linguistic system based on the observable output which results from a learner’s attempted production a TL (target language) norm. This linguistic system we will call “interlanguage” (IL)’ Selinker, 1974: 35). Selinker (1974: 35) reported five processes central to second language learning:

- language transfer
- transfer of training
- strategies of second language learning
- strategies of second language communication
- overgeneralization of target language linguistic material

These processes are described below in some detail.

Language Transfer

Language transfer is an important factor in second language learning. The linguists like Selinker believe that the mother tongue sometimes facilitates and sometimes interferes and hinders the second language learning. The term transfer signifies the transfer of learner’s native language habits to the target language. When the transferred habits are acceptable in the target language, the learning of the second language is facilitated and becomes easy to acquire it. But when they are unacceptable, interference is caused and the process of learning becomes a little tough as the learner has to put an extra effort to shun his previous habits and learn new ones. There are two types of transfers: positive and negative. In case of similarities between MT and TL, the positive transfer occurs. In such settings, the

role of MT is that of facilitator of second language acquisition. To be very precise, the second language learners acquire those features of TL with ease which exists in their MT. In contrast, the dissimilarities between MT and TL result in negative transfer. In such areas of dissimilarities, MT of the learner interferes in the acquisition of the features of TL. Thus divergences and deviations in the sentences of the second language learner could be well attributed to language transfer.

Transfer of Training

The second language learners overlearn those structures which are regularly presented to them in the textbooks and examples and drills given by the teachers. For instance, the Serbo-Croatian speakers almost always use *he* even at those places where *she* is required. This difficulty cannot be attributed to the language transfer as Serbo-Croatian has the same distinction between *he* and *she* as English (cited in Selinker 1974: 39). This is due to transfer of training as the textbooks and the teachers in this interlingual situation present examples and drills always using *he* and never with *she*. After sometime this gets fossilized in their interlanguage and they regularly use *he* in place of *she* feeling that they do not need to make this distinction in order to communicate.

(Selinker, 1974: 39).

Strategies of Second Language Learning

The second language learners use some strategies in their attempt to master the target language and express meaning in it. It has been pointed out that these strategies are culture bound to some extent. It has been argued that strategies for handling the target language material evolve when the learner realizes his incompetence with regard to some aspects of target language. Various internal strategies on the part of the second language learner affect, to a large extent, the surface structure of sentences underlying Interlanguage utterances. But exactly what these strategies are and how they work is at present a pure conjecture (Selinker 1974: 40). Some of the strategies may be simplification of the target language rules and avoidance of complexities in target language. For example:

- Don't worry, I am hearing him. (Selinker 1974: 40)

Strategies of Second Language Communication

The second language learner uses various strategies in the use of his Interlanguage. Their focus is on the process of participating in a conversation and getting meaning across or clarifying what the speaker intended. He may use simple structures and avoid the use of complex structure. He may do so due to the fact that the second language learner is not very confident of his ability to use the complex structures or he has to make a conscious effort for using these complex structures which he does not want. For example:

- It was Ø nice, nice trailer, Ø big one. (Selinker 1974: 40)

Overgeneralization

Overgeneralization of the target language rules is a phenomenon very common to the second language learners. The second language learners discover certain generalizations in the target language on the basis of the limited input of the target language. They start using these self explored rules in their Interlanguage. For instance:

- What did he intended to say? (Selinker 1974: 38)

Here the past tense morpheme –ed is extended to an environment in which, to the learner, it could logically apply, but just does not.

A combination of these processes produces entirely fossilized Interlanguage competence of the second language learner. Interlanguage fossilization is a stage during second language acquisition. When mastering a target language, second language learners and foreign language learners develop a linguistic system that is self-contained and different from both the learner's first language and the target language (Nemser, 1974: 55). This linguistic system has been variously called interlanguage (Selinker, 1974), approximative system (Nemser, 1974: 55), and idiosyncratic dialects or transitional dialects (Corder, 1974: 158).

Bilingual Child

We can categorise the bilingual language acquisition according to the ages at which both languages are acquired. It can be categorised as infant language acquisition, child language acquisition, adolescent language acquisition and adult language acquisition. I am discussing only adult and child language acquisition in a bilingual context and will use the term 'child' for both the terms. Taking bilingual child into consideration is an entertaining and insightful activity. Even at the age of two or three children have two languages at their disposal, as it has been found that their proficiency in both the languages is not similar. Many children, like children of parents of cross-cultural marriages, grow up in families where more than one language is spoken and to a great extent in bilingual communities. There is a majority of children who are not exposed to two languages from birth but they frequently start learning second language when they enter schools in which, basically, the medium of instruction is the languages other than their mother tongue. This kind of education pattern is quite prevalent in India which is especially known as linguistic diversity, especially for bilingualism. Many children grow up with two languages. They have to learn two sound systems, two morphological systems, two lexicons, two syntactic systems, and two sets of systems for use.

Process of Acquisition

The process of bilingual first language acquisition is almost similar to first language acquisition. The bilingual child learns two languages in the same way and in the same order as the monolingual child learns one, with obvious difference that the bilingual child has to learn distinguish between the two. But the mechanism which helps the bilingual children to differentiate between two languages is different in nature from that of monolinguals. So, we can say that bilingual does not require any special mental processes, but only extension and refinement of those common to language speakers

Conclusion

We as humans have a capacity to acquire human languages. This capacity enables us to abstract and internalize the rules underlying the materials to which we are exposed as children. Exposure is very important to activate the innate capacity that enables us to acquire language. If a child is not exposed to human language within the critical period (puberty age), the ability to acquire language is lost. Second language learning begins usually after the instinctive capacity for language acquisition has matured to some extent. It may be true to some extent that the increasing difficulty of learning with age may be related to the loss of the elasticity of the brain mechanism. In addition, second language learning requires some adjustments with the culture imparted through the language. His habits, intelligence, aptitude, attitudes, motivation and other psychological and linguistic factors may facilitate his learning or may inhibit him from learning the second language. Personality factors and motivation play a very important role in the acquisition of second language. Yet at the same time one must take into account the psychological and social factors that may facilitate or hamper the acquisition of a second language.

In general, the ability to learn a second language varies from person to person. Some of the reasons for these differences may be ascribed to age, motive, native skills, intelligence, aptitude, attitude, role of learner's mother tongue, personality, auditory memory span, readiness to learn, emotion and drive.

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